

PSYCHOLOGY OF PATIENTS IN CEREBRAL STROKE

Makhamadjonov Jakhongir Zakirjon oqli

2nd year student of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology of Fergana State University

Latipova Feruzakhon Jamolovna

2nd year student of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology of Fergana State University

Nabiyeva Nigorakhon Shukhratjon kizi

2nd year student of the Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology of Fergana State University

Abstract: In this article, based on medical psychology, we present our views on the subject of psychology of stroke patients.

Keywords: stroke, brain stroke, paralysis, pathological change, hemianesthesia, monoanesthesia, medical-psychological process.

An acute disturbance of blood circulation in the brain is called a stroke, and this disease is manifested not only by neurological disorders, but also by neuropsychological disorders of various degrees. Neuropsychological syndromes observed in stroke patients in Uzbekistan Z.R. Deeply studied by Ibodullayev (1999-2009). Brain strokes are one of the most common diseases, and sudden neurological disorders leave severe complications in the patient's psyche. The acute onset of this disease in a patient who was considered healthy only yesterday, due to sudden paralysis in the limbs, he is bedridden, unable to understand the words of those closest to him, or does not even speak a single word. inability to speak is a great disaster for both the patient and his relatives. Pathological changes observed in cerebral stroke depend on the area of the brain where the disease has developed, the type of disease, the size of the affected area, and the period of the stroke. Detailed information about this is given in neurology textbooks and training manuals. Almost 70 percent of cerebral strokes are observed in the a. cerebri media area, which supplies a large part of the outer surface of the cerebral hemispheres with blood. Because this artery is the direct successor of the internal carotid artery. A. cerebri media supplies blood to the centers of movement, sensation and speech, therefore, acute blood circulation disorders in this artery cause paralysis of the limbs (hemiparesis, monoparesis), sensory disturbances on one side of

the body (hemianesthesia, monoanesthesia) and manifested by speech disorders (motor and sensory aphasias). [4, 89]

If a stroke develops in the left hemisphere of the brain, paralysis (hemiparesis) and sensory disturbances (hemianesthesia) on the right side of the body are manifested with speech disorders (aphasias). If a stroke occurs in the right hemisphere of the brain, paralysis and sensory disturbances are observed on the left side of the body, but there are no speech disorders. It should be noted that speech disorders are observed when the left hemisphere of the brain is damaged in the left-hand side of the brain, in the case of the right hemisphere, and in the case of ambidextrous, it is observed when both hemispheres are damaged. However, speech disorders in ambidextrous and ambidextrous people recover faster than in ambidextrous people. [5, 254]

Behavioral disorders observed in stroke are different when the left and right hemispheres of the brain are damaged. Manifestation of limb paralysis together with speech disorders (motor and sensory aphasias) is a severe psychological trauma for the patient. The sudden disruption of speech, which makes a person different from other creatures, changes the psychology of the unconscious, he hears everything around him only in the state of sound, does not understand the meaning, and cannot explain his thoughts, as a result of which the patient becomes a jerk, his loved ones He fights, he tries to speak rudely, but he cannot express his thoughts correctly. [7, 89]

This condition is typical for sensory aphasia (the second chapter of the textbook provides detailed information on the clinical presentation and diagnosis of aphasia). Sometimes the patient lies silent, only tries to answer the questions of those around him, answers simple questions, but does not speak. This condition is typical for motor aphasia. Speech is usually restored earlier than in paraplegics, for example, in the early stages of a stroke. The rate of rapid recovery of speech largely depends on the type of stroke, the size of the damaged area and, of course, how the treatment process is carried out. [8, 69]

Thus, the treatment of stroke patients and their return to a normal lifestyle is a long-lasting complex medical and psychological process, the successful completion of which depends on the correct and timely treatment.

References:

1. Tolipov U., Usmanbayeva M. Pedagogik texnologiya:nazariya va amaliyot.- T.: "Fan". 2005.
2. Iqboljon O'g'li, Tojimamatov Jamshidbek, and Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh Alisher o'g'li. "THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON." *PEDAGOGS jurnali* 9.3 (2022): 4-7.
3. Khakimov, Mukhammad Khodjakhonovich, and Azimjon Latifjon ugli Melikuziev. "The History of Paralinguistic Researches." *International Journal of Culture and Modernity* 13 (2022): 90-95.
4. Akhmedov, A., and O. Egamberdiyev. "PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS." *Science and innovation* 1. B4 (2022): 136-138.
5. Alisher o'g'li, Egamberdiyev Oyatillokh. "Issues of Retraining and Professional Development of Pedagogical Personnel." *The Peerian Journal* 5 (2022): 192-194.
6. Tojimamatov, Jamshidbek, and Oyatillokh Egamberdiyev. "THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON." *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research* 2.5 (2022): 470-473.
7. Khakimov, M. K., & ugli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). The History of Paralinguistic Researches. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 13, 90-95.
8. ogli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(10), 126-128.
9. Vasila Karimova. Salomatlik psixologiyasi. -T .: 2005.
10. Визел Т.Г. Основы нейропсихологии. -М .: 2000.